

Environmental Scan Summary

The following provides an overview of neighbourhood assets and potential barriers/gaps for older adults. The features were identified through a structured assessment in June 2019. As such, this summary should be viewed as an overview of key features observed rather than an exhaustive list.

Most houses observed in the Strathcona and Dundurn neighbourhoods are older, two-story, brick buildings tightly built next to each other. Some taller and newer apartment buildings are scattered within the neighbourhood. The neighbourhood appears to be ethnically diverse as it is home to many ethnic places of worship (e.g. Lithuanian, Korean, Chinese). The area has many parks and green spaces where families and individuals walking dogs were observed. Several fitness centres were also noted. Along main roads, traffic was busy, and individuals could be seen walking about. Narrow residential streets were crowded with many parked cars. Bus routes and bicycle lanes were noted on major roads such as King Street West, York Boulevard, and Dundurn Street North. Aside from the Strathcona Elementary School, the Nicholas Mancini Centre hosts a wide range of programs for early learning and childcare.

Strathcona/Dundurn seems well serviced with medical clinics, dental clinics, and pharmacies, as well as the Canadian Hearing Society. Though there were a few single-practitioner clinics throughout the neighbourhood, it was noted that some of the health services were clustered together in plazas (e.g., Kingwest Plaza, Main Street Plaza). Strathcona/Dundurn is also home to major grocery stores such as Fortinos, fast food outlets like Tim Hortons and McDonald's, a Dollar Store and convenience stores.

Strengths of Strathcona/Dundurn include its diversity and number of services (observed through ethnic restaurants and places of worship), as well as its strong sense of community (families seen socializing in parks). Strathcona/Dundurn has medical

clinics, grocery stores and parks distributed throughout the neighbourhood. Bus routes and bike lanes exist along major roads which supports access to resources within and outside of Strathcona/Dundurn for those living close to these busy streets. However, an individual's ability to get around within the neighbourhood may be limited for older adults who live away from these major routes. Strathcona/Dundurn lacks the necessary infrastructure to provide accessible transportation for these residents. Narrow residential streets limit bus access and bike lanes.

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Map of services identified in Strathcona and Dundurn

Index of services in Strathcona and Dundurn

Map Number	Description
Education	
1	Hess Street Public School
2	Strathcona Elementary School
Fitness/Recreation	
3	De La Sol Yoga Studios
4	Inland Island Community Wellness Centre
5	SAM Good Shepherd*
6	Studio Zee Pilates
7	Sturgess Cycle Fitness Centre
8	Victoria Park Pool*
9	Zee Float
Food Sources	
10	B & T Food
11	Fortinos
12	Good Convenience
13	Hess Variety
14	McQueen's Banh Mi Viet
15	Pho Lac Vien
16	Pho Nhung
17	Select Convenience 24 hrs
18	Select Food Mart and Pizza
19	The Mustard Seed Co-operative Grocery
20-23	Tim Hortons

Health/Social Services

24	Altima Hess Village Dental Centre
25	Banyan Community Services
26	Canadian Hearing Society
27	Dr. Adina Radulescu Dental Office
28	Dr. Jarecka Dental
29	Dundurn Medical Centre Inc.
30	Dynacare Laboratory and Health Services Centre
31	Energy Tap Counselling and Consultation Service
32	Hess Village Compounding Pharmacy
33	King Medical Pharmacy
34	Kingwest Medical Associates
35	Medical Pharmacy-Farmacia
36	Melissa Mitchell, RMT
37	Nicholas Mancini Centre
38	Ontario Early Years Centre
39	Performance Physiotherapy
40	Queen York Pharmacy
41	Service Ontario
42	Shoppers Drive-Thru Pharmacy

Housing

43	Good Shepherd
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Parks

- 44 Cathedral Park
- 45 Harvey Park
- 46 Kay Drage Park
- 47 [Victoria Park](#)

Protective Services

- 48 [Hamilton Fire Department - Station 11](#)

Religious Centres

- 49 [Hamilton Chinese Alliance Church](#)
- 50 [Hamilton Christian Fellowship](#)
- 51 [Korean United Church](#)
- 52 [Our Lady of Mercy Lithuanian Church](#)
- 53 [St. Demetrios Greek Orthodox Church](#)

Retail Stores

- 54 Drop Off Cleaners & Laundry
- 55 Radfan Convenience
- 56 [The Wash](#)
- 57 [Your Dollar Store with More](#)

*Programs targeted specifically at older adults

Environmental Scan Update, 2022

The neighbourhood's programs and services appeared relatively consistent with those available in the initial environmental scan completed in 2019. The initial environmental scan identified a total of 54 services; currently 55 services have been identified. Minor changes are seen in the number of services across service categories in fitness/recreation, and health/social services (Table 1). These changes can be attributed to services no longer being operational due to COVID-19-related closures, and changes in the categorization of services e.g., the Inland Island Community Wellness Centre, which previously was listed in fitness/recreation services, has been permanently closed. In terms of new services, Circle of Friends for Newcomers (Hamilton), an organization that provides English classes for newcomers, was identified, and categorized within health/social services. Similarly, the Employment & Education Resource Centre, which provides support for seeking employment and further education, was a new service identified within the health/social services category.

The COVID-19 pandemic had varying degrees of impact on service delivery within the community (Table 1). Most of all identified services in 2022 remain open and serve the community in person. A detailed list of services within the Strathcona and Dundurn neighbourhood and their current operational status (as impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic) is shown in Table 2. It is notable that it was consistently observed throughout the process of updating the environmental scan that the COVID-19 pandemic affected channels of online communication (websites, online bulletins and blogs). Many websites and online communications were not regularly updated (especially with smaller, more local services). As such, the visibility and accessibility of such services have been impacted.

Moreover, as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic there were some changes in ownership, management, and name of services. One of the most notable changes

seemed to be the renaming of the Mustard Seed Co-operative Grocery, to the Strathcona Market. While the ownership and name has changed, the function of the organization has stayed the same - to serve the community with wholesome, local products, and enable food services and programs such as the Strathcona Community Pantry – where community members can take or leave non-refrigerated foods and essential goods.

Table 1. Summary of Number of Services Identified 2019-2022 and COVID-19 status

Service Category	Number of Services (2019)	Number of Services (2022)	Open, in-person	Open with online options available	Unclear status	Closed
Education	2	2	2			
Fitness/ Recreation	6	5	2	1	2	1
Food Sources	14	14	14			
Health/Social Services	17	19	15	2	2	
Housing	1	1	1			
Parks	4	4	4			
Protective Services	1	1	1			
Religious Centres	5	5	3		2	
Stores	4	4	3		1	
Total	54	55	45	3	7	1

Table 2. Summary of Services: COVID-19 Status and Function

Open, in-person (with modified procedures for public safety)	Open with online options available	Unclear status (with attempt to contact)	Closed	
Education				
Hess Street Public School Strathcona Elementary School				
Fitness/Recreation				
Victoria Park Pool SAM Adult Day Programs (Good Shepherd)	De La Sol Yoga Studios	Studio Zee Pilates Zee Float	Inland Island Community Wellness Centre	
Food Sources				
B&T Food Fortinos Hess Variety McQueen's Banh Mi Viet Pho Lac Vien Pho Nhung Select Convenience 24 Hrs Select Food Market and Pizza Strathcona Market* Tim Hortons (4 locations)				Good Convenience
Health/Social Services				
Altima Hess Village Dental Centre Banyan Community Services Dr. Adina Radulescu Dental Office Dynacare Laboratory and Health Services Centre Hess Village Compounding Pharmacy King Medical Pharmacy Kingwest Medical Associates Medical Pharmacy Performance Physiotherapy Queen York Pharmacy Service Ontario Shoppers Drive-Thru Pharmacy Employment & Education Resource Centre Circle of Friends Hamilton				Canadian Hearing Society** Energy Tap Counselling and Consultation Service Melissa Mitchell, RMT

Open, in-person (with modified procedures for public safety)	Open with online options available	Unclear status (with attempt to contact)	Closed
Housing			
Good Shepherd			
Parks			
Cathedral Park Harvey Park Kay Drage Park Victoria Park			
Protective Services			
Hamilton Fire Department - Station 11			
Religious Centres			
Hamilton Chinese Alliance Church Hamilton Christian Fellowship Korean United Church		Our Lady of Mercy Lithuanian Church St. Demetrios Greek Orthodox Church	
Stores			
Radfan Convenience The Wash Your Dollar Store with More		Drop Off Cleaners & Laundry	

*Strathcona Market previously operated under the name “Mustard Seed Co-operative Grocery”

**Canadian Hearing Society’s (Strathcona location) physical operation is temporarily closed however some services and programs *are being* delivered through online platforms

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Siddiqui S., Nadarajah A.. on behalf of the EMBOLDEN research team (2023). Environmental scan: Strathcona and Dundurn. URL: <https://emboldenstudy.mcmaster.ca/projects-results/>

Institute for Research on Aging

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Public Health Agency of Canada

Agence de la santé publique du Canada

LABARGE CENTRE FOR MOBILITY IN AGING

CT Highlights

 Population
= 3,131

 Number of Homes
= 1,836

 Population Density
= 2,539/Km²

 5-year Population change = -0.3%

Age Distribution by Gender

Age 55+

42%

Age 25-54

39%

Age 0-24

19%

\$39,000

Average Income
(after-tax)

Income & Employment

Prevalence of Low-income by Age (%)

13.9%

Unemployment
Rate

Citizenship & Immigrant Population

Canadian Citizens

94.3%

Immigrants

26.5%

Recent Immigrants

2.8%

 Recent Immigrants by Birthplace

 Immigrants by Birthplace

Language Spoken at Home

English | 84.8%
Non-official Languages | 12.0%

Highest Certificate, Diploma or Degree

- No certificate, diploma or degree
- Secondary (high) school diploma or equivalency
- Postsecondary certificate, diploma or degree

Neighbourhood Homes

Average monthly shelter costs

Rent their home

Average home value

Apartment > 5 stories

Built before 1980

Major repair needed

Public Health Agency of Canada Agence de la santé publique du Canada

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Data Source: Statistics Canada. 2021. 5370047.00 [Census tract].
www.statcan.gc.ca

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